

Breeding box for Pipunculidae, Berlin, West Germany. 1

places in Berlin. Two other GLH species, *Turrutus socialis* (F1.) and *Mocuellus collinus* (Boh.), also are parasitized.

Twelve- to 15-d-old *Vicia faba* plants were used to feed *E. incisus*. Parasitized hoppers were released on the plants. Pipunculid larvae that emerged successfully pupated in the box. Pupae were transferred to petri dishes containing sterilized sand placed inside the box. To avoid desiccation, sand was moistened with few drops of tap water at 3-d intervals. Emergent flies were fed diluted honey (6 cc water/g honey) on small pieces of blotting paper or cotton to simulate the honeydew secretions of leafhoppers on which the flies naturally live. Blotting paper and cotton were changed every 2 or 3 d.

When the flies had mated, a large number of first- to third-instar nymphs of *E. incisus* were released on the plants for parasitization by Pipunculidae. One such test consisted of 8 flies (4 males + 4 females) and about 150 *E. incisus* nymphs. Sixty-five *E. incisus* were parasitized. Female parasites preferred second- to third-instar nymphs for oviposition.

Parasite larval duration was 29 to 32 d, calculated from the date of oviposition to emergence of larva from the host. Pupal duration was 9 to 21 d. Adult flies lived for 4 to 11 d.

Our studies indicate this breeding method is successful for Pipunculidae that emerge from the first generation of leafhoppers in summer. □

Insecticidal control of the rice yellow stem borer (YSB)

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We evaluated the efficacy of eight emulsifiable concentrate insecticides and a wettable powder for control of YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* in a field experiment, in 1983 rabi. Maximum protection—seedling root dip in chlorpyrifos 0.02% for 12 h followed by quinalphos 1.0 kg ai/ha at 20, 40, and 60 d after transplanting (DT)—and untreated check treatments were included for comparison. Insecticides were applied 22 and 60 DT.

One application at 22 DT with 0.75 kg ai/ha quinalphos, ethion, triazophos, bromophos, monocrotophos, Mipcin

Efficacy of spray formulation insecticides for control of YSB, Coimbatore, India.^a

Insecticide	Dose (kg ai/ha)	Deadhearts (%)	Whiteheads (%)	Yield (t/ha)
Cypermethrin (Ripcord 10 Ec)	0.10	8.5 bc	7.8 d	2.1 cd
Triazophos (Hostathion 40 Ec)	0.75	3.8 ab	5.7 cd	3.4 b
Bromophos (Nexion 35 Ec)	0.75	4.1 ab	4.1 bc	3.2 bc
Monocrotophos (Monocil 40 Ec)	0.75	4.2 ab	3.3 ab	3.6 b
Ethion (Tafethion 50 Ec)	0.75	3.4 ab	5.5 bc	3.4 b
Quinalphos (Kotophos 25 Ec)	0.75	3.0 a	4.5 bc	3.5 bc
Mipcin 50 WP (MIPC 50 WP)	0.75	4.2 ab	4.5 bc	3.2 bc
UC 54229 99 SP ^b	0.75	4.7 ab	6.1 cd	3.0 cd
RH 0994 45 EC ^b	0.75	5.2 abc	8.2 de	3.3 bc
Maximum protection ^c		1.6 a	2.0 a	4.8 a
Untreated check		11.2 c	11.2 e	2.4 d

^a In a column, means followed by the same letter are not significantly different at 5% level DMRT.

^b Technical name not available. ^cSeedling root-dip in chlorpyrifos 0.02% for 12 h followed by quinalphos 5G @ 1.0 kg ai/ha at 20, 40, and 60 DT.

(MIPC 50 WP) or UC54229 significantly reduced deadheart damage, and produced results similar to those of maximum protection (see table). Two sprays of mono-

crotophos effectively reduced whiteheads. Monocrotophos 0.75 kg ai/ha most effectively reduced YSB infestation at tillering and flowering. □

Toxicity of insecticides to the predatory mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* Reuter

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The mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* is an effective predator of rice hopper eggs and nymphs. We assessed the toxicity to the mirid bug of some commonly used rice insecticides. With an atomizer, potted 45-d-old TN1 rice plants were sprayed

Toxicity of insecticides to the mirid bug *C. lividipennis*, Coimbatore, India.

Insecticide	Formulation (%)	Corrected mortality (% T. V.) ^a at indicated time after spraying		
		1 d	3 d	5 d
Endosulfan	0.07	34.72 a	7.40 a	20.63 a
Neem oil	5	36.90 a	38.11 bcd	20.01 a
Carbaryl (50% WP)	1.0	49.59 a	81.99 e	46.02 a
Phosalone	0.07	62.15 abc	46.36 bcde	36.07 a
Monocrotophos	0.08	65.67 abc	60.85 de	53.96 a
Chlorpyrifos	0.04	83.51 bc	60.58 de	33.25 a
Quinalphos	0.075	90.00 c	50.08 cde	41.85 a

^a In a column means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at P = 0.005, T. V. = Arc Sin√percentage transformed value.